

Development of Rubber Economy in Binh Phuoc Province (1997-2010)

Du The Hung ✉

Thu Dau Mot University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

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Abstract

During the period 1997–2010, the rubber economy of Binh Phuoc province experienced strong development, gradually affirming its role as a key economic sector in the local agricultural structure. Based on advantages in natural conditions, land fund and production traditions, along with the system of guidelines and policies to encourage the development of perennial industrial crops of the State and province, the area of rubber cultivation, output and yield continuously increased. The rubber industry mainly developed according to two models: smallholder rubber and large-scale rubber, contributing to mobilizing social resources, forming specialized cultivation areas associated with the processing industry, creating jobs and improving income for rural people. However, the development process still faces limitations such as dependence on market fluctuations, unreasonable product structure, unsustainable production efficiency and impacts on the environment.

Keywords: *Rubber economy, Binh Phuoc, economic development, perennial industrial crops.*

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Introduction

In the process of innovation and economic integration, Vietnamese agriculture has had important changes, in which the development of perennial industrial crops plays a key role in promoting economic growth, shifting production structure and improving the lives of rural people. Rubber is one of the key industrial crops, not only with high economic value but also contributing to solving employment, increasing export turnover and sustainable development of rural areas. Binh Phuoc is a province in the Southeast region, with favorable natural conditions of land and climate for rubber development. Since 1997, along with the re-establishment of the province and the implementation of economic development policies of the Party and State, the rubber industry in Binh Phuoc has had strong

development in terms of area, output and economic value. Rubber gradually became a spearhead economic sector, making an important contribution to the socio-economic development of the locality. However, the rubber economic development process in Binh Phuoc in the 1997-2010 period also revealed certain limitations such as dependence on the world market, price fluctuations, unstable production efficiency and impacts on the ecological environment. Systematically studying the rubber economic development process in this period is necessary to clarify the limitations and causes, serving policy planning and sustainable development orientation for the rubber industry in the following periods.

Historical Context

International Context

During the period 1997–2010, the world context had many profound changes in economic, political, scientific and technological aspects, strongly impacting the development trend of commodity production industries, including the natural rubber industry. After the end of the Cold War, economic globalization emerged as the dominant trend of the world economy, driven by rapid advances in science and technology, especially in the fields of information technology, production automation and global logistics systems. According to E.A. Roberts (1952), pp.77-78), the demand for natural rubber consumption both domestically and internationally tends to increase rapidly, mainly due to the strong development of the automobile and motorcycle tire manufacturing industries and the medical field. Specifically, global natural rubber consumption increased from 6.019 million tons in 1996 to 8.180 million tons in 2004, achieving an average annual growth rate of about 3.78% in the 1996-2004 period. From 2006, the world and regional economies had positive changes; peace, cooperation and international economic integration were strengthened, creating favorable conditions for increasing flows of trade, investment and capital. In that context, the Asia-Pacific region in general and ASEAN in particular continued to maintain dynamic development speed.

The international financial and monetary market and world commodity prices fluctuated complexly; natural rubber prices were unstable, causing difficulties for consumption and production and business planning. In particular, the global financial crisis and economic recession in 2007–2008 reduced the demand for rubber consumption, negatively impacting the Vietnamese economy and the rubber industry. Thus, the international context in the 1997-2010 period created both opportunities and challenges for the rubber industry in terms of competitiveness, technology and ability to adapt to the market. In that trend, Binh Phuoc, with its advantage of basalt red soil, favorable natural conditions and long-standing rubber cultivation tradition, has the conditions to restructure the

industry towards expanding scale, improving productivity and participating more deeply in the global value chain.

Domestic Context

After 1997, when Binh Phuoc province was re-established on the basis of separation from Song Be province, the local socio-economic conditions had clear changes, creating an important premise for the development of the rubber economy. This was the period when the Binh Phuoc rubber industry developed strongly, under the impact of economic innovation and a synchronous system of policies to encourage from the Central to local levels. However, the Asian financial-monetary crisis in 1997 negatively affected the regional and Vietnamese economies, reducing market demand, causing price fluctuations and slowing down the development momentum of the rubber industry in the late 1990s. Based on the industrialization and modernization path identified from the VIII Congress of the Party, agriculture and rural areas were placed at the center of the development strategy, in which perennial industrial crops, especially rubber, were considered an important pillar of the commodity agriculture associated with processing and export industries. After more than a decade of innovation, the transition to a socialist-oriented market economy has created a favorable environment for mobilizing social resources, attracting investment and innovating production methods in the rubber industry in the direction of improving efficiency and competitiveness. The State has issued many important guidelines and policies to promote rubber development, such as the agricultural development strategy to 2010, credit, land, agricultural extension and seed and technical support policies; while promoting smallholder rubber development and restructuring the industry towards linking production with processing. The completion of the economic institution, especially the 2003 Land Law, along with the process of deep international integration, especially after Vietnam joined the WTO in 2006, has expanded export markets and enhanced the role of rubber in the structure of key export commodities.

At the local level, Binh Phuoc province has proactively issued plans and policies to support the development of the rubber industry, identifying rubber as a key industrial crop in the socio-economic development strategy. The unity and synchronization in the policy system from the Central to local levels has created a favorable environment, attracting many economic sectors to participate, contributing to promoting the rubber economy of Binh Phuoc to develop strongly and gradually affirm its role as a spearhead economic sector in the 1997–2010 period.

Rubber Economic Development Activities in Binh Phuoc in the 1997-2010 Period

Guidelines and Policies for Rubber Development

After re-establishing the province in 1997, Binh Phuoc implemented guidelines for rubber development based on thoroughly grasping the Central's general direction on promoting industrialization and modernization of agriculture and rural areas. In the context of the urgent need to convert the crop structure, rubber was identified as one of the key long-term industrial crops, suitable to the natural conditions and commodity economic development orientation of the locality. Prioritizing rubber development reflects a strategic choice to effectively exploit land resources, while creating a stable source of income for the provincial economy. The policy of rubber development in Binh Phuoc after the re-establishment of the province was closely linked to the renovation policy established at the VIII National Congress of the Party (8/1996). This Congress marked an important turning point in the development thinking of the Communist Party of Vietnam, after exceeding the socio-economic goals of the 1991-1995 period. Based on summing up the renovation practice, the Party set out a 5-year plan for 1996-2000 with the orientation to continue developing a multi-component economy operating under the socialist-oriented market mechanism, in which agriculture was identified as a key area that needs to be reorganized towards commodity production. In that context, the resolutions of

the VIII Congress and further affirmed at the IX Congress clearly defined the role of rubber in the economic development strategy in key provinces, including Binh Phuoc. Rubber is not only considered a long-term industrial crop with export value but also an important tool to exploit land potential, create jobs and improve the lives of rural residents. The orientation of rubber industry development is concretized through the requirement to increase investment, expand production scale and improve processing capacity, with the goal of increasing latex processing capacity from 20,000 tons/year to about 70,000 tons/year, while forming concentrated production areas associated with on-site processing industry (Communist Party of Vietnam, 1996, pp. 167–168).

Based on that general direction, the Central Government continued to issue important policies to promote rubber industry development. Resolution No. 10/NQ-TW in 1998 on renovating agricultural management expanded the autonomy of production, creating conditions for household economies to participate in rubber cultivation. Credit policies, especially Decision No. 67/1999/QĐ-TTg, contributed to removing difficulties in capital, while setting a target of developing about 700,000 ha of rubber throughout the country. These orientations created a favorable policy framework for localities, including Binh Phuoc, to proactively implement rubber development plans suitable to actual conditions.

At the provincial level, the Binh Phuoc provincial government has proactively issued plans for rubber industry development, focusing on providing high-quality seeds, transferring advanced cultivation techniques, supporting preferential loans and implementing land tax exemption and reduction policies for rubber growers. In the socio-economic development orientation, Binh Phuoc province has clearly identified the strategic role of agriculture, especially key industrial crops such as rubber. The Resolution of the VI Provincial Party Congress emphasized the requirement to create a new change in investment and agricultural economic development towards commodity production associated with processing, while affirming that the province's agricultural

economy plays an extremely important role, as a condition to accelerate the province's economic development speed, especially processing industry from agricultural and forestry products. Accordingly, the main development direction of the industry is to build a comprehensive and modern agriculture, closely linked to market demand, promoting product diversification and increasing added value. In that context, rubber is considered one of the key pillars, contributing to promoting processing industry, creating jobs, and improving income for rural people. In order to encourage the sustainable and effective development of the rubber industry, Binh Phuoc province has issued many legal documents showing the local government's deep concern for this field. Typically, Decision No. 1129/QD-UBND dated May 22, 2008 approving the plan for rubber industry development in the province and Official Letter No. 3154/UBND-KT dated December 5, 2011, which emphasizes supporting investment and promoting the application of scientific and technical advances into production. In addition, the annual agricultural extension funding support policy has played an important role in improving knowledge, skills and production capacity for rubber growers, especially in rural, deep-lying and remote areas. These policies demonstrate the province's determination to develop the rubber industry into a key economic sector, contributing to promoting agricultural economic growth and improving people's lives. In general, the synchronization and consistency in the policy system from the central to local levels has created a favorable environment, attracting the participation of many economic sectors, from state-owned enterprises, private enterprises to household economies, making an important contribution to the strong development of the

rubber economy of Binh Phuoc province in the 1997-2010 period.

Expansion of Rubber Planting Area and Yield

Since its re-establishment, the area of industrial crops in Binh Phuoc province has increased rapidly. In the period from 1997 to 2011, the area of industrial crops in the province increased 2.3 times, equivalent to an additional 216,378 ha. In 1997, the area of industrial crops in the province was 163,004 ha, but by 2011 it had increased to 379,382 ha. In which, the fastest growing period was from 2005 to 2007, when the area increased by 72,315 ha, equivalent to 1.3 times compared to before. According to Le Huu Phuoc and Giang Van Khoa (2013, p.62), the rapid increase in rubber area in Binh Phuoc in the period after 2005 is closely related to the orientation and agricultural development policies set out at the VIII Provincial Party Congress (term 2005-2010). At this Congress, the province clearly identified the key tasks to promote agriculture to develop in a sustainable and effective direction. Specifically, the provincial government has focused on reviewing the planned land fund, thereby proposing measures to exploit and use land reasonably, prioritizing the allocation of suitable land to expand the area of key crops. In addition, the province also promoted investment in high-yielding and high-quality crop varieties, especially rubber and cashew. Policies to support the application of science and technology into production, intensive farming, improving productivity and quality of agricultural products have helped improve economic efficiency in agricultural production. As a result, rubber products gradually have higher competitiveness in the market, becoming the dominant driving force in the local agricultural economic structure.

Table 1. Area and Output of Rubber Trees in the Province Period 1997 – 2010

Year	Area (ha)	Area for production (ha)	Yield (tons)	Yield (quintals/ha)
1997	77.670	38.303	36.277	9,47
1998	82.159	42.816	46.727	10,91
1999	84.319	44.990	54.089	12,02
2000	86.961	51.162	67.000	13,10
2001	84.057	52.200	68.891	13,20
2002	88.327	60.913	71.716	11,77
2003	88.738	67.195	81.117	12,07

2004	90.641	72.804	92.505	12,71
2005	99.178	77.489	110.562	14,27
2006	110.562	82.445	131.386	15,94
2007	118.151	84.194	147.520	17,52
2008	133.809	86.598	160.564	18,54
2009	144.024	91.143	172.911	18,97
2010	164.179	98.262	191.837	19,52

Source: Author's synthesis from socio-economic statistical data of Binh Phuoc province in the 1997 - 2010 period

In 1997, the whole province had 77,670 ha of rubber, but the area for products only reached 38,303 ha (accounting for 49.3% of the total area), and more than half was newly planted area. The yield also only reached 0.95 tons/ha and the output was 36277 tons/ha. By 2000, the total area had increased to 86916 ha, an increase of 11.9% (an increase of 9246 ha) compared to 1997. In which, the area of latex exploitation reached 51162 ha, an increase of 33.6% (an increase of 12859 ha) compared to 1997. The output reached 67000 tons, an increase of 84.7% (an increase of 30723 tons) compared to 1997. In 2001, the total rubber area of the province was 84057 ha, a decrease of 3.34% (a decrease of 2904 ha) compared to 2000. The area for products was 52200ha, an increase of 2.03% (an increase of 1038 ha) compared to 2000. By 2002, the area had increased to 88327 ha, an increase of 17.7% (an increase of 10657 ha) compared to 1997. The area for products increased high to 60913ha, an increase of 9% (an increase of 22610 ha) compared to 1997 (Hiep, 2003, p. 59). Since 2005, rubber prices in the market have continuously increased, accompanied by policies on contracting, converting forest land, improving depleted forests and converting low-economic crops to rubber cultivation, which has promoted the rubber area of the province to increase sharply. By 2011, the total rubber area of the province had increased to 203,427 ha from 99,178 ha in 2005, an increase of 104,249 ha with an average rate of 12.7% per year. However, the reality shows that the rubber area of the province is much larger because the area of withered rubber in the province is increasing rapidly (Huynh Thi Kieu Hoa, 2013, p.84).

In terms of cultivation, the rubber area in the province increased rapidly, especially from the early 2000s, thanks to the advantage of a large

land fund, suitable soil and climate conditions, along with policies to encourage the development of long-term industrial crops of the State and local authorities. Rubber has gradually replaced a part of the traditional crops with low economic efficiency, becoming the main crop in the province's agricultural structure. This area expansion process contributes to the formation of concentrated rubber farming areas, creating an important material foundation for the development of the industry in the following stages.

Smallholder and Largeholder Rubber Development Models in the 1997 - 2010 Period

Development process and characteristics of the smallholder rubber model

After being re-established in 1997, Binh Phuoc province faced an urgent need to effectively exploit land potential, solve employment and improve income for rural residents in the context of a low economic starting point. In that context, the application of the Central's policies on allocating land stably and for a long time to households, encouraging the development of long-term industrial crops has created an important institutional foundation for the formation and expansion of the smallholder rubber model in the province. To expand the land fund to serve the development of rubber material areas in the context of increasingly limited public land funds, Binh Phuoc has gradually implemented a model of association between rubber enterprises and households through the form of contributing capital with the value of land use rights. Accordingly, people participating in the project become shareholders, sharing responsibilities, benefits and risks with the enterprise throughout the rubber production

and business cycle. This model not only creates conditions for accumulation and concentration of land for large-scale rubber production, but also contributes to harmonizing the relationship between the interests of enterprises and farmers, limiting the situation of land fragmentation and conflicts in the project implementation process.

From the perspective of the industry economy, the form of people contributing capital with land use rights in Binh Phuoc is considered a new production organization method, suitable to the requirements of restructuring the rubber industry in the direction of improving the efficiency of land resource use. This model helps enterprises reduce input cost pressure for the stage of creating a land fund, while creating a stable and long-term source of income for households participating in the project through dividends and other benefit distribution payments. Through this, the rubber industry of Binh Phuoc has the conditions to expand the material area associated with sustainable development, strengthen production links along the value chain and improve competitiveness in the context of increasingly deep international economic integration. The mechanism of long-term land use rights allocation, associated with expanding autonomy in agricultural production, has created conditions for farmers to actively invest in rubber cultivation as a long-term livelihood choice. At the same time, the increasing demand for rubber in the domestic and international markets, along with expectations about the relatively stable economic efficiency of rubber trees compared to traditional crops, has promoted the conversion of cultivated land to rubber cultivation according to the household model, especially in rural areas and new economic zones.

In the period 1997–2010, smallholder rubber in Binh Phuoc developed rapidly in both area and the number of participating households. This model is mainly household-based, with a cultivation scale of several hectares to several tens of hectares, directly invested, managed and organized for production by households. The initial investment capital mainly relies on household accumulation, credit loans and certain support in terms of seeds and techniques from specialized agencies or state-owned rubber

enterprises in the area. Regarding cultivation techniques, smallholder households gradually learned from the experience of the state farm system and agricultural extension programs, but the level of application of scientific and technological advances was not uniform. The exploitation and consumption of rubber latex is mainly through traders or sold directly to processing plants, making smallholder rubber growers significantly dependent on market price fluctuations as well as the ability to access information of each production household.

Limitations and issues raised by the smallholder rubber model

Besides the positive role in expanding the area of rubber cultivation and improving income for people, the smallholder rubber model in Binh Phuoc in the 1997–2010 period also revealed many structural limitations. Due to the small and scattered production scale, smallholder households face difficulties in accessing long-term capital sources, applying synchronous science and technology and improving product quality. The consumption of rubber latex mainly through traders makes rubber growers vulnerable to unfavorable market fluctuations, especially in periods of deep rubber price decline. In addition, the process of expanding the area of smallholder rubber in this period is mostly spontaneous, not closely linked to land use planning and sustainable development orientation of the locality. This not only increases the risk of imbalance in the crop structure but also poses problems about the environment, such as soil quality degradation and pressure on ecological resources.

Overall, in the period 1997–2010, the smallholder rubber model played an important role in the rubber industry's economic development process in Binh Phuoc. This is both a direct product of the agricultural innovation process and a driving force to promote production expansion and stabilize farmers' lives in the early years after the re-establishment of the province. However, in essence, this model still mainly develops in breadth, relying heavily on area expansion and exploiting natural advantages, while the level of production links, organization level and ability to

withstand market risks are still limited. Those characteristics show the inevitable requirement to adjust and upgrade the smallholder rubber model in the period after 2010, towards strengthening value chain links, promoting the application of science and technology and linking production development with the goal of socio-economic stability and environmental protection.

Development process and characteristics of the largeholder rubber model

In parallel with the development of the smallholder rubber model, the largeholder rubber model continued to play a key role in the rubber industry's economic development process in Binh Phuoc in the 1997–2010 period. This is a model inherited directly from the plantation and state farm system formed before, and is organized, adjusted and operated according to the new requirements of the market economy in the context of Renovation and integration. After the re-establishment of the province, Binh Phuoc received a system of state-owned rubber farms with a large concentrated land scale, a relatively stable labor force and material-technical facilities formed from the previous stage. In the context of local limitations on investment resources, the largeholder rubber model is identified as the core force to ensure maintaining output, stabilizing budget revenue and creating jobs for workers.

The establishment of the Vietnam Rubber Group in the mid-1990s created conditions for unified management, planning and coordination of the operations of state-owned rubber enterprises, in which the units based in Binh Phuoc played an important role. On that basis, the largeholder rubber model in the province was strengthened in terms of management organization, production scale and development orientation associated with the market. In the period 2006–2010, Binh Phuoc province converged many favorable conditions for rubber industry development, including a large land fund, suitable soil and climate conditions, abundant labor force, and a favorable geographical location in regional and trade links. These factors created an important opportunity, helping the rubber industry of Binh Phuoc

continue to expand production scale, improve the competitiveness of natural rubber in the domestic and international markets.

Besides the natural advantages, the attention and direction of the Party, State and Government for the rubber industry in general has created a favorable policy foundation for Binh Phuoc to promote production development and reorganize business operations in a more efficient direction. The policy of expanding rubber planting area in the province received the consensus and support of all levels of government as well as people. Besides the favorable conditions, in the period 2006–2010, the process of rubber industry development in Binh Phuoc province still faced many difficulties and challenges. First of all, the policy of investing in rubber industry development has not been truly unified between the development orientation of largeholder and smallholder, leading to confusion in implementation and resource allocation. This lack of synchronization has caused many obstacles for rubber enterprises in implementing specific policies, especially in planning and managing rubber planting land funds. In addition, due to historical characteristics and different natural conditions between regions, rubber enterprises in the province have uneven scale and development level. Some large units, formed early, have advantages in land area, climate conditions, production location and relatively complete infrastructure systems, so they achieve high production and business efficiency. In contrast, small-scale, newly established units or those developed on old rubber areas with limited areas face many difficulties in organizing production, investing in infrastructure and improving productivity. In addition, unfavorable weather, diseases on rubber trees, along with the spreading impact of the world financial-monetary crisis have negatively affected the production and business operations of the rubber industry in Binh Phuoc, dragging along the consequences of jobs and income of workers. The structure of rubber products in this period is still monotonous, mainly latex, not meeting well the increasingly diverse requirements of the market; the proportion of industrial rubber products with high added value

is still low, limiting the ability to improve the economic efficiency of the industry.

On the other hand, in the context of increasingly deep regional and international economic integration, especially when the commitments in the framework of AFTA and APEC take effect, the level of competition in the rubber market is increasingly fierce. Meanwhile, the mechanism and policies to support the rubber industry still reveal inadequacies; management capacity, technology level and competitiveness among enterprises are not uniform, leading to production and business results, revenue and profit margin not commensurate with the potential of land resources and the scale of assets assigned to manage. To meet the development requirements in the context of the domestic, regional and world situation *diễn biến phức tạp*, intertwined between opportunities and challenges in the period 2006–2010, reorganizing the operation model and improving the management capacity of the rubber industry became an urgent requirement. On that basis, in order to ensure the successful implementation of the 5-year Plan 2006–2010, the Vietnam Rubber Group proposed to the Government to allow the conversion of the operation model towards an economic group, thereby expanding the scale of production and business, improving financial capacity, management and international integration capacity. This policy is especially meaningful for key areas such as Binh Phuoc province, where a large rubber area is concentrated, playing a key role in the raw material area structure of the whole country. The formation of an economic group model creates conditions for rubber enterprises in Binh Phuoc to promote the advantages of land, labor and production scale, while strengthening internal industry links, improving the efficiency of resource use and the ability to adapt to fluctuations in the world market.

On October 30, 2006, the Prime Minister issued Decision No. 248/2006/QĐ-TTg approving the Pilot Project on forming the Vietnam Rubber Industry Group and Decision No. 249/2006/QĐ-TTg on establishing the parent company – Vietnam Rubber Industry Group. This is an important legal basis, creating

an institutional corridor for the rubber industry in general and the rubber industry in Binh Phuoc in particular to promote organizational restructuring, improve production and business efficiency and gradually integrate more deeply into the regional and world economy. During the period 1997-2010, the largeholder rubber model in Binh Phuoc was mainly managed by state-owned enterprises and member companies of the rubber industry, with a large concentrated planting area, a relatively closed production process from planting, care, exploitation to latex processing. Compared to the smallholder model, largeholder rubber has a clear advantage in terms of capital mobilization, labor organization and synchronous application of scientific and technological advances. Largeholder rubber enterprises gradually innovated the management mechanism towards increasing autonomy in production and business, linking the responsibility of units and workers with economic efficiency. The application of contracting within enterprises, combined with investment in innovation of processing technology, has contributed to improving productivity, latex quality and the competitiveness of rubber products in the market. Thanks to promoting the application of scientific and technological advances synchronously from the seed stage to the cultivation process, the efficiency of rubber production in specialized farming areas has been clearly improved. Strict compliance with technical procedures in planting and care has contributed to improving the survival rate of trees after planting, reflecting the quality of garden investment and the efficiency of capital use. The average survival rate in the Southeast region reached over 93%, while in the Central Highlands and some central areas it reached about 85%, showing the relatively good adaptation of rubber varieties in different ecological conditions. Favorable climatic conditions, especially relatively evenly distributed rainfall, have created a stable growing environment for rubber trees, helping the garden maintain 2–3 sustainable layers of leaves, thereby improving photosynthesis and biomass accumulation. On that basis, rubber enterprises have gradually expanded the area of new

planting according to the contracting method associated with the volume and quality of work, in order to increase initiative and efficiency in production organization. This model contributes to controlling initial investment costs, while improving the responsibility of workers in the basic construction process, creating a premise for improving productivity and economic efficiency of the garden in the subsequent exploitation cycle.

For commercial gardens, rubber enterprises in the area have focused on completing the technical management of latex exploitation in the direction of standardizing the process and improving the efficiency of garden use. The focus is on organizing exploitation according to the correct latex tapping technical process, regularly training and improving skills for exploitation workers to ensure that the tapping line meets technical requirements, limiting the phenomenon of tapping the tree body, thereby maintaining stable productivity and prolonging the business cycle of the garden. Along with that, the latex tapping regime is adjusted flexibly according to weather conditions and ecological characteristics of each region. In the summer, when the temperature is high and growing conditions are favorable, the tapping time is arranged earlier; In contrast, in winter or periods of low temperature, latex tapping is implemented later to reduce physiological damage to the tree and limit production decline. Based on the specific climate of Binh Phuoc province, enterprises have strengthened the application of technical support measures such as using rain covers, tree body covers on the entire latex exploitation area. This measure contributes to reducing the number of tapping days off due to rain, limiting latex loss and improving exploitation efficiency in the rainy season, thereby improving the economic efficiency of commercial gardens.

The rubber latex processing technology process in this period was gradually innovated in the direction of improving economic efficiency and standardizing products. Rubber latex is organized and processed according to the national standard CSV system, ensuring requirements for quality, uniformity and marketability. From being mainly dependent on

imported equipment, the rubber industry has gradually mastered technology in the stage, forming facilities capable of designing, manufacturing and assembling rubber latex processing machinery and equipment as well as replacement components and accessories for production. Proactive equipment and technology not only contribute to reducing investment costs, lowering product prices, but also improving the flexibility and operational efficiency of processing plants. Typically, the commissioning of latex lines with a capacity of about 1,500 tons of latex/year, meeting processing needs associated with concentrated raw material areas, thereby gradually improving processing capacity and added value of the rubber industry.

In terms of product structure and consumption market, rubber processing activities in Binh Phuoc are deeply *đặc trưng* of a large-scale plantation production model, with advantages in latex collection conditions and the stability of the raw material source. The proportion of rubber products of the province still focuses mainly on common technical rubber block types, especially SVR 3L, accounting for about 75% of total output. This is a group of products with stable consumption demand but low added value in the world market. Meanwhile, the global natural rubber market mainly serves the tire manufacturing industry, a field that consumes about 70% of total natural rubber output, with high requirements for technical rubber types such as SVR10, SVR20 and equivalent products. However, the rubber product structure of Binh Phuoc is still limited in terms of the proportion of these product lines, reflecting the low level of participation in the high-value and technically demanding market segment. For latex (concentrated latex), although this is a product suitable for largeholder production conditions and has relatively large demand in the glove, medical and technical rubber product industries, the proportion of *ly tâm* latex in the province's total processing output is still very low, only about 4%. This unreasonable product structure is one of the reasons for increasing market risk, making the rubber industry of Binh Phuoc strongly affected by world rubber price fluctuations and facing difficulties in improving

economic efficiency as well as long-term competitiveness. In general, since chuyển sang a new organization and management model towards production - business (from 1995), rubber enterprises in Binh Phuoc have gradually promoted initiative in allocating and using resources, improving production management capacity and adapting to the market mechanism. On that basis, the province's rubber industry has promoted product structure diversification, gradually from simple raw material production to developing product lines with higher technical standards and added value, in order to improve production - business efficiency.

Rubber enterprises not only create large volumes of commodity products for export, but also contribute significantly to the local budget, promoting the development of processing industry and supporting service industries. Besides the economic role, largeholder rubber also has a clear social meaning when creating stable jobs for tens of thousands of workers, including migrant workers and ethnic minorities. Through social welfare activities, building infrastructure, housing, schools and health care, largeholder rubber enterprises have contributed to stabilizing the population, promoting the process of and rural development in production areas. Along with the process of renovating production organization and improving business efficiency, the living conditions of the labor force in the rubber industry have been gradually improved clearly. Workers are arranged with stable housing, have a fund of secondary production land for cultivation, animal husbandry and intercropping short-term crops such as fruit trees, coffee, pepper, etc., thereby contributing to diversifying livelihoods and improving household income. Thanks to that, most workers feel secure long-term with rubber gardens, creating a stable foundation for production organization and labor management in enterprises. At the same time, the system of social institutions at rubber farms is gradually completed.

Limitations and issues raised

Although holding the dominant role, the largeholder rubber model in the period 1997–2010 also revealed no small limitations. The state

enterprise management mechanism is still heavily administrative, slow to adapt to market fluctuations, leading to production - business efficiency not commensurate with the potential of land and labor. Large management costs, a cumbersome apparatus and dependence on world rubber prices make some enterprises face difficulties when the market fluctuates. Although Vietnam in general and Binh Phuoc in particular are among the leading rubber producing and exporting countries in the world, many studies suggest that the competitiveness of the rubber industry is still low and not commensurate with the potential. The main reason is the export structure raw and latex, limited added value, heavily dependent on the international market and lack of effective links between stages in the value chain (Vuong Quoc Thang, 2012, pp.56-57). In addition, the expansion of largeholder rubber area in this period mainly relied on exploiting land advantages, not closely linked to the requirements of environmental protection and sustainable development. The lack of consistency in the orientation of rubber industry development at the macro level, especially between the development model towards largeholder and smallholder, has directly affected the organization of production and implementation of investment in the locality. In the context that Binh Phuoc is a place where many large-scale state-owned rubber farms and companies are concentrated, the slow completion of a unified management mechanism has led to problems in production management and effective use of land resources. Along with that, the management of rubber planting land planning in Binh Phuoc in this period also revealed certain limitations. Some localities have not built a suitable management method to ensure the stability of the land area planned for rubber enterprises, leading to difficulties in expanding production, gardens and long-term investment. The scale and production capacity between rubber units in the province also have significant differences: companies with a long history of formation, owning large land funds and relatively complete infrastructure systems often achieve higher production - business efficiency; meanwhile, small-scale or newly formed units face many

limitations in capital, technology and the ability to organize production according to the value chain. In addition to internal factors, the rubber economy of Binh Phuoc is also adversely affected by objective factors such as erratic weather, diseases on rubber trees, as well as the spreading impact of the global financial-monetary crisis in 2007–2008. These factors have increased production risk, causing price and product consumption fluctuations, directly affecting the business efficiency of rubber enterprises in the area. At the same time, the structure of rubber products of Binh Phuoc in this period is still monotonous, mainly focusing on latex, the proportion of deeply processed products and industrial rubber products is still low, not fully meeting the requirements of improving added value and competitiveness in the context of increasingly deep international economic integration.

Those limitations raise the requirement to continue innovating the organization model, improving management efficiency and strengthening links with the smallholder sector in the next development stage. It can be affirmed that, in the period 1997–2010, the largeholder rubber model was the pillar of the rubber industry's economy in Binh Phuoc, holding the role of stabilizing production, ensuring raw material supply and leading the overall development of the industry. However, the development of this model still bears the strong imprint of the transition period from the planned mechanism to the market economy, with limitations in flexibility and efficiency. Those characteristics show that, the period after 2010, the largeholder rubber model needs to be restructured towards modernizing enterprise management, more closely with the market and with the smallholder rubber sector, in order to improve competitiveness and hướng tới sustainable development of the rubber industry's economy in Binh Phuoc.

Conclusion

The period from 1997 to 2010 marked a significant stage in the development of Binh Phuoc province's rubber economy amidst Vietnam's extensive economic reforms and integration. Based on its advantageous natural

conditions and vast land resources, coupled with the impact of a comprehensive system of policies and guidelines from the central to local levels, the rubber industry in Binh Phuoc experienced rapid growth in terms of acreage, production, and its role in the agricultural economic structure. Rubber gradually affirmed its position as a key industrial crop, contributing to economic growth, the restructuring of agricultural production, job creation, and increased income for rural residents. The development of the rubber economy in Binh Phuoc during this period showed a blend of two main production models: small-scale and large-scale rubber cultivation. Small-scale rubber cultivation flourished, becoming a crucial driving force in mobilizing social resources, expanding rubber plantations, and improving the livelihoods of farming households. However, this model also reveals limitations such as small-scale production, low levels of linkages, limited application of science and technology, and limited resilience to market fluctuations. Conversely, the large-scale rubber plantation model plays a pivotal role in ensuring production, stabilizing raw material sources, and leading the overall development of the industry, but it is still affected by the state-owned enterprise management mechanism, an irrational product structure, and economic efficiency not commensurate with its potential. Besides the achievements, the rubber economy of Binh Phuoc during the period 1997–2010 also faced many challenges, especially its heavy dependence on fluctuations in the world rubber market, a product structure skewed towards processed latex with low added value, and certain impacts on the ecological environment. These limitations reflect a development that is still heavily focused on extensive expansion, relying heavily on increasing cultivated area and exploiting natural advantages, while insufficient attention has been paid to the depth of technology, management, and value chain linkages.

From the practical experience of rubber economic development in Binh Phuoc during the period 1997–2010, several important scientific implications can be drawn: the development of the rubber industry needs to be placed within the overall strategy of restructuring

agriculture towards sustainability; strengthening linkages between smallholder and large-scale rubber plantations; promoting the application of science and technology, improving product quality, and expanding deep processing to increase added value and competitiveness. These conclusions are not only significant in re-evaluating the development process of the rubber industry in Binh Phuoc, but also provide a scientific basis for policy planning and development orientation of the rubber industry in subsequent periods.

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